

Case Report

Disfluencies in debate genre: A Case of world university students debate championship

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Abstract

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This paper focused on university debate genre. The data for the paper was derived from world university debate championship. It involved recording of the corpora which were transcribed into written form. The corpora were usually characterized by a huge number of sentences which were disfluent. The elements which made a sentence not fluent were commonly referred to as 'disfluencies'. Repetition of words uttered previously, complete corrections or restarts of sentences were some of the common features of students' debate genre. When a speaker deleted elements considered to be disfluent in a given speech situation, s/he was left with only the intended meaning representations which could be considered clean. While some disfluencies were intentional while others were habitual, yet, others were side effects of anxiety, inadequate vocabularies, inefficient discourse knowledge, etc. The research revealed world University students' debate championships were characterized by three major types of disfluencies: pause/fillers, repeats, and self – corrections. Statistics indicated that long unlexicalized pause a:m has a highest and it was attributed to unfamiliarity with some debate topics, due to short notice issued to participants prior to commencement of the tournament, hence they lacked right lexicons to use.

Keywords: Debate, discourse, disfluency, genre, transcriptions.

INTRODUCTION

Genre analysis is a current and strong influence on understanding language use. It is defined as abstract, socially recognized ways of using a language. Thus, genre analysis shows a genuine interest in the use of language to achieve communicative goals through a dynamic explanation of the way experts of a language manipulate generic conventions to achieve a variety of complex goals by combining sociolinguistic perspectives, especially the use of ethnographic information with those of cognitive perspectives.

To participate in specialist communicative events, such as debates or any form of language practice, one needs to be acquainted not only with the communicative goal of a discourse community, but also with the purpose associated with specific uses of genre.

Statement of the Problem

Living together as social beings posits constant responsibilities for members of numerous groups to which people belong- groups in places of work, worship, towns, cities, and nation at large. Students' being members of any of these sub groups mentioned and future leaders need to gather information, scrutinize, evaluate, accept, or reject pieces of information for proper policy making. This means that wise future citizenry depends significantly on skills, knowledge and dispositions acquired through different communicative means. To engage in healthy debates or arguments is to accept the possibility that one's opinion could either be falsified, or proven wrong. Unfortunately, teacher-student,

doctor-patient, lender-debtor, boss-subordinate, husband-wife, parents-children, seller-customer, parliamentarians, etc. who consciously or otherwise engage in arguments or debates of various kinds for divergent reasons which would have been resolved in civilized manner end up using derogatory terms, threats, insults, interruptions etc.

Furthermore, in order to promote and sustain democracy, there is a great demand for the public speaking constructions in all schools irrespective of the nation's economic growth, or social standards. This explains that all students are expected to receive sophisticated and relevant education regardless of their specific locations, social status, race, religious beliefs, political ideologies, etc and one of the standard areas is actually language art which is better met by practicing debates and its associated component skills.

The present-day students are socially active and wish to mingle freely with their counterparts through various communicative means. Unfortunately, most school authorities see debate as a venture which is used to advertise their school academic attainment. This is why debate exercise is considered significant from its competitiveness instead of academic and social benefits. Consequently, only few 'intelligent' ones are required to represent their schools in forensics competitions while the majority rarely interact with even with their fellow schools mates. The absence of these extra curricula activities in many schools renders the students ineffective listeners and speakers.

Despite pedagogical significance of debate in schools, and in politics, it is sad to note from empirical studies that debaters become increasingly involved in ethics that are unwarranted.

Literature

Genre analysis offers explanations to many of the mysteries of the way members of various discourse communities' function to achieve goals and their institutionalized disciplinary goals to justify their discursive practices. In fact, one of the main objectives of genre analysis is to account for the realities of the 'world of texts'. The real world is dynamic, and complex in the sense that it incorporates texts of various kinds, serving often overlapping and at the same time conflicting communicative purposes. The complexity lies in the following ways as presented by Bhatia (2002):

1. Although genre analysis is identified on the basis of conventionalized features, yet we know genres are constantly developing Berkenkotter and Hucker (1995).
2. We often find typical textualization patterns, yet we know expert members of professional communities exploit them to create novel forms. Berkenkotter and Hucker (1995).
3. We know that genres serve typical socially recognized

communicative purposes, yet we often find genres being exploited to convey private intentions, Bhatia (1995).

4. We all manage to identify the individual generic artifact, yet in the real world they are often seen in hybrid, mixed and embedded forms, (Bhatia, 1995).

5. Genres are given typical names, yet different members of discourse communities have varying perspectives on and interpretation of them, which are sometimes contested, as in Bhatia (1995).

6. We believe that genres are independent of disciplinary variations, yet we often find disciplinary conflicts in many of them, especially in academic genres Bhatia (1995).

This study presents genre analysis of debates, an interactional approach to discourse organization. The paper argues that genres are basic and conventionalized communicative events imposed by norms, purpose, etc. of the discourse community of learners who are university students from all over the world. The study accounts for the variety of factors interwoven in the organization of language use. This explains that the study of genre consists of analyzing traces left by such communicative practices of audio by means of various semiotic artifacts such as transcriptions. The implication is that, beyond a description of social and linguistic conventions of debates, the study of language use constitutes a legitimate and relevant domain of investigation for applied linguistics research as real data enables the study of complex speech represents actual discourse practices. Consequently, analyzing argument implies recognition of complex relation between particular discursive events and the situations, institutions and social structures which frame them.

Genre analysis is viewed as an act of linguistic explanation, attending to answer the question, 'why do members of a specific discourse community use language the way they do? The answer requires input not only from linguistics, but from sociolinguistics, ethnography, cultures and insight from members of a discourse community.

Genre analysis assumed that language is used differently within different cultures, and that second language proficiency lies in the mastery of the different genres of the target language (Crossley, 2007). This means that second language proficiency is a matter of realizing genres and subgenres, and the ability to demonstrate these movements from one level to the next.

While it is too broad to analyze the whole debate genre considering space, this paper is restricted to disfluncies emerging from various socio – linguistic factors.

In speech, or writing, people edit, and plan their utterances before intended messages are realized phonetically during communication, Boars et al (2007). This implies that speakers are monitoring their speech production processes, Postman (2010). As people perceive language that does not correspond to their communicative intent, their speech repair apparatus may

be activated. This is called repairs. People's self – repairs imply the existence of specialized control devices or 'monitor' which verify the 'correctness' of ongoing activity, and response output, Postman (ibid). Simply put, self – repair is a quality control Hieke (2001). While Schegloff et al. (1977) say that repair is a device that intercepts pre – articulatory, and post – articulatory deviations made by speakers inadvertently. If the addressee in a speech situation directly points out the mistakes made by other speakers in the presence of many other listeners, the addresser's positive face can be damaged at least to a certain extent (Brown and Levinson 1987).

In order not to devastate their listeners' face in public debates, listeners remain unvoiced even if they notice the slip – ups. However, in speaking, people's speech blunders could be noticed and pointed out by other interlocutors rather than the speaker. This type of repair is called other – initiated repair, (Khodadady, 2012). Furthermore, Schegloff et al. (ibid) identify four types of repair in their investigation i.e. self – initiated, self-repaired, other – repair, and other initiated – repair.

Following the insights from (Schegloff et al., 1977), (Rieger, 2000, p. 48) defines repair as error correction, the search for word, and the use of hesitation, pauses, lexical, quasi – lexical, or non – lexical pauses, fillers, immediate lexical changes false starts, and instaneous repetitions (p.48). Contrastively, O' Connell and Kowal (2015) disagree with the above, and argue that the course of spoken language can never be literary fluent. Rather, it is characterized by disfluencies – pauses, elongated segments, fillers (such as er -, a: m) editing expressions such as *I mean, you know*, word fragments, self – corrections and repeated words, and most disfluencies seem to reflect improper planning. Consequently, speakers suspend their speech and introduce pauses or fillers before proceeding, or change their minds about what have been said, add to, delete, or replace words which have already been reproduced.

The act of reproducing another, 'correct words' is a sort of commitment which speakers have to make in order to fulfill their communicative obligation, which may not be accidental in all occurrences. In fact, it has been argued that some types of disfluencies should be accounted among the tools speakers have for communicating message to the listener, alongside others (such as tone of voice) which sometimes may be caused as a result of the speaker's own editing his/her speech. Sometimes, disfluencies may be due to unfamiliar topics of the debates.

The Concept of Debate

In many developing countries in Africa and Asia with complex and numerous societal demands in areas such as: security, politics, economy, climate, population, religious differences, diseases, divergent human

demands and feelings; solutions to these multiple global issues, are sometimes temporary and imperfect. Consequently, people do not agree on definitions, or existence as the public holds different views, values, beliefs, styles, policies, based on divergence in cultures, traditions, origin, qualifications, interest, goals, etc. hence the need for debate over public issues.

Debate is a common phenomenon in people's daily life as people either consciously or unconsciously engage in formal, or informal debate of different types for either personal, or public reasons. Debate generally is defined as a contention, dispute, controversy, disagreement, etc. over certain unresolved issues, because of its significance to humanity, it is carried out in order to make certain laws effective (only in parliamentary).

In parliamentary democracies, debates are held for various reasons ranging from people contesting for public offices, policy debating so as to enact certain laws, etc.

Debate is often held in public places as, broadcast on TV, radio, and/or the Internet. Outcomes of debates may be decided by voting, by judges, or by combination of both. Debate communication is characterized by the following:

1. Interaction of two or more people;
2. Face-to-face interaction (excluding Internet debate);
3. Spoken, formal/informal speech;
4. Social distance: ranging from minimal to maximal;
5. Purpose is to 'win over' the other participants and/or the audience;
6. Argumentation: challenging opponents' views;
7. Social status of participants: approximately equal;
8. Field of discourse: non-specific, highly controversial.

Nowadays, students from college and university campuses in many parts of the world, engage in organized debates. It can be used as a very successfully tool in classroom discussions. Competitive and in-class debate serves several important objectives:

1. Debate offers unique opportunities to relate often abstract classroom theories to 'real world' issues in areas that are interesting to most students.
2. Debate provides significant education experience. Obviously, students learn about the processes of 'debate' and decision-making during the activity. Additionally, debate utilizes skills such as: public speaking, logic, persuasion, organization, research, composition and other skills relevant to such a complex act.
3. Debate encompasses an element of play and competition that attracts and stimulates students; promote the educational process.
4. Individual skills learned through debate have a broader impact on society as well. Specifically, debate can equally help fledgling democracies from wounds inflicted by oppressive dictatorships and ethnic violence, or religious mishaps by providing a forum where volatile issues can be openly discussed. Also, newly enfranchised citizens who engage in such debate may acquire first-hand knowledge on how democracy works.

5. Debate teaches principles of tolerance, non-violence and respect for different points of view by closing the gap between minority and majority cultures, and other groups divided by long-standing differences.

6. Debate serves as a way to foster international understanding, cooperation, and a free and lively exchange of ideas. In bringing together students from around the world from vastly different backgrounds, debate offers much more than contesting of formal argumentation. By its convention, debate breaks boundaries, showing that opposing views can be explained in a way that connects rather than divide people. As a process, debate both embodies and encourages peaceful discussion rather than aggressive confrontation.

To engage in a healthy and comprehensible debate, participants should be both genre and context sensitive. Fortunately, the genres of students' debates comprise a variety of genres of multiple disciplines because debates encompass distinct and current issues that affect society which include religion, health, security, international and global issues, etc.

Debate Format and Duration

There are several different formats. Most of these formats share general features. Specifically, all structured debates have two sides: a proposition and an opposition side. The function of the proposition side is to advocate the adoption of the resolution, while the duty of the opposition is to refute the resolution. The resolution can take different forms, depending on the format, but in most cases, policy or statement. For instance, 'This House believes that...' or 'Be it resolved that...'

Team policy debate is one of the most popular debate formats practiced in the United States. The Proposition side is called, 'the affirmative' or government and the opposition party is referred to as 'negative side'. Each side is composed of a team of two debaters, so that there are four people participating in the debate.

A round team policy debate consists of eight speeches. The first four speeches are called constructive speeches because the teams are perceived as laying out their most important arguments during these speeches. The last four speeches are rebuttals, because the teams are expected to extend and apply arguments that have already been made, rather than making new arguments.

Below is a Table 1 showing speakers' turns and time allotted.

The Flow of Arguments

New arguments can be made at any time during the first four discourses. Nevertheless, new arguments cannot be made during rebuttals. The PMR can retort to new

opposition arguments that were made during the MO. The PMR can encompass new retorts, but not new arguments.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is premised on two theories. First, Cooperative Principles introduced by Grice in 1975. It is associated with its attendant maxims which together regulate the exchange of information between individuals involved in interactions. Grice has established a set of general principles with the aim of explaining how language users communicate indirect meaning (conversational implicatures), i.e. meanings which have to be inferred from what is being said explicitly on the basis of logical deduction. The cooperative principle is based on the assumption that language users tacitly agree to cooperate by making their contribution to the talk as is required by the current stage of the talk, or the direction into which it develops. Adherence to this principle entails that speakers simultaneously observe four maxims.

1. Quality, i.e. make your contribution truthful, and sincere.
2. Quantity, i.e. provide sufficient information.
3. Manner, i.e. make your contribution brief, present it in an orderly fashion.
4. Relation, i.e. make your contribution a relevant one.

The second theory was proposed by Schegloff and his friends in 1977. They argued that in speaking, people's speech blunders could be noticed and pointed out by other interlocutors as well as the speaker himself/herself. This type of repair is called other – initiated repair, or self – initiated repair. Schegloff et al. (ibid). Furthermore, Schegloff et al. (ibid) identified four types of repair in their investigation which include, self – initiated, self- repaired, other – repair, and other initiated – repair.

Following the insights of Schegloff et al. (1977) repair is referred to as error correction, the search for word, and the use of hesitation, pauses, lexical, quasi – lexical, or non – lexical pauses, fillers, immediate lexical changes false starts, and instantaneous repetitions. They are characterized by disfluencies – pauses, elongated segments, fillers (such as er -, a: m) editing expressions, word fragments, self – corrections and repeated words, and most of the disfluencies seem to reflect improper discourse planning by the participants and in order to effect the earlier errors, the speakers suspend their speech and introduce pauses or fillers before proceeding, or changing their minds about what have been said.

METHODOLOGY

The materials for this paper comprised excerpts from

Table 1. Speakers' turns and time allotted.

The Government team, a Prime Minister will speak twice, and a Member of Government will speak once.	Prime Minister Constructive	PMC	7 Minutes
	Leader of the Opposition Constructive	LOC	8 Min.
The Opposition team, a leader of the Opposition will speak twice, and a Member of the Opposition will speak once.	Member of the Government Constructive	MGC	8 Min.
	Member of the Opposition Constructive	MOC	8 Min.
The Government put forward a precise case declaration, which they should prove it to be correct and valid.	Leader of Opposition Rebuttal	LOR	4 Min.
	Prime Minister Rebuttal	PMR	5 MIN.

world debating championship which took place in Thessalonica, Greece during 2016 competitions where 400 university students cross the world converged on Thessalonica to contest for various trophies. The researcher retrieved the data from YouTube.

Each debate was listened repeatedly so as to grasp the whole discourses. For analysis sake, the speeches were first transcribed to a level of detail that captured all words and words fragments audible to the ear as. This became necessary because the language people use becomes research data only if it is transposed from its original source of production to the activity in which it could be analyzed. Also, transcribed were non lexical filler such as a: m, er and other vocalization.

The transcription was made easy through the use of a soft ware called adobe audition which made the speeches slow such that the videos must not be subjected to rewind severally in order to hear the exact sound produced. After that, the researcher had to cross check the transcripts while listening to the videos. The transcripts were then imported into sequence, coding and analyzing types, numbers and sequences of behavioral events.

Transcribed speech was coded as disfluent if it contained any of the following categories: repeats, self – corrections, and fillers. Where one disfluency occurred right after another, they were coded as separate disfluencies. If there were several disfluencies on the same type in a row (e.g. several repeated tokens of the same word), these were coded individually as well. Materials were counted as repeats only when they were repeated by the same speaker (as opposed to being echoed by team members).

The research methodology adopted in this article involved both qualitative and quantitative techniques as they both help to provide empirical evidence of certain linguistic trends and give account for their occurrences.

The greatest challenge the current researcher faced in dealing with the analysis was related to the issue of measuring pause lengths, emerging from inaccessibility of

advanced speech analysis equipment which rendered it impossible to determine with precision the duration of pauses. Nevertheless, pause lengths were assessed from a relative to the apparent speech rate of the debate contexts. Therefore, each break in the speech continuity was considered as a pause if it exceeded 5 - 6 seconds. When the pause lasted between 2- 4 seconds, it was considered very brief; it was termed, 'short'. On the other hand, when a pause lasted beyond 6 seconds, it was considered so long as it distracted the flow of the debate, it was deemed long.

Analysis

The analysis was carried out using subheadings followed by relevant illustrations to buttress empirical claims. Occurrences of disfluent speeches are classified and numbered (1, 2, etc.) followed by explanations.

Long and unlexicalized pauses: a: m

Excerpt (1). On – a: m, a: m going to get a: m going to get our first speaker's argument about the role of government.

Excerpt (2). We as government compensate them first by a: m – providing fund to, actually a:m restart, and develop the technology.

Excerpt (3). But first of all, we like to question the side proposition and a: m – ask them whether...

Excerpt (4). The government is not there to monitor its people and they protect people from a: m – kind of kind of harm.

Short unlexicalized Pause er

Excerpt (1). We believe right to information is a basic right of a person and a person get er – er – is born.

Excerpt (2). When you see a woman er – er -, when you see a woman er – objectifying like that er – the first thing er – that comes er – is identity.

Excerpt (3) we said earlier, this is damage to idea er – er –of er – er – to the Feminist Movement.

Repeats

Excerpt (1). We are trying to promote something like that.

Excerpt (2). We are trying to achieve development.

Excerpt (3). We are trying to achieve globalization.

Excerpt (4). Just because you don't understand the Wikipedia, would you, would you restrict the social media of the people, just because you don't understand the Wikipedia of other people.

Excerpt (5). you don't know exactly what kind of work, what kind of er – er – work you are going to undertake.

Excerpt (6). If a play let, if a play let is highly skilled then...

Excerpt (7). when you see a woman er – when you see a woman er- objectifying...

Excerpt (8). That's not a healthy way of solving a conflict.

Excerpt (9). That's not a healthy way of bringing up a resolution.

In all the illustrations indicated above, repeats display a variety of linguistic functions. For instance, in (1, 2, & 3), the repeats are uttered by the same speaker, and they occur in the same discursive environment as listing which serve the function of clarifications. The speaker is able to display some sort of artfulness by varying the complements of the proposition, *to* in each of clauses while clauses (4, 5, 6, & 7) are results of unstable speech situations probably caused by distractions, while (8 & 9) are pragmatically used to double up the illocutionary force i.e. to persuade via the device of emphasis. The commonest occurrence of repeats is the one used as a scaffolding act to help speakers to recall eluding memories.

Self – corrections

The term, 'self – corrections or repairs' are commonly understood to refer to the replacements of 'unpleasant, unintended, 'errors' or 'mistakes' by what are considered to be 'correct'. However, a word search can occur if an item (e.g. a word) is not available to a speaker when 'due' but not a replacement of a 'correction'. Self – corrections are speech results from complicated interplay of perceptual and production processes. In order to make a repair, the speaker must firstly notice some trouble and interrupt his/her flow of speech, and secondly create a new utterance which takes care of the trouble and its potential consequences for the listener. See illustrations below:

Excerpt (1). The first speaker of the Opposition

mentioned that no limited er – talking about online education...

Excerpt (2). We Members of the proposition – the Opposition said access to education is a crime.

Excerpt (3). We don't believe that the playboy, playmates are objectified – they should be allowed, they, the feminists should support them in their part.

Excerpt (4) ...men's monopoly, that er – the feminists – the main discourse is monopolized by Feminist Movement.

Excerpt (5) ...because, imagine the tricks – I will show you how you have watched the movie.

Excerpt (6). We need an extremist idea – ideology.

Excerpt (7). We go to another argument which – where the proposition recognized that the music industry is not focusing on big artistes.

Excerpt (8). The government mainly should not...mainly er – er – in putting, bringing profit and loss ladies and gentlemen.

Excerpt (9). They teach a person how to live in a married life, not only – sorry- er – emotional...

Excerpt (10). If you go – you take a couple that had not gone through any counseling session, and...

In (8), the repair is not correct itself; it leads to a staggering of additional repairs, 'putting' but a final correction is made, 'bringing'. In (3), there is no problem with the start because the replacement of 'play lets,' with 'playboy' does not alter the construction as well as the intended meaning. However, in (4), a complete search necessitates the hitches in which the speaker struggles to select the right choice. Similarly, in (1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, & 10), the speakers ramble, and search for correct lexical items and finally replace them with the correct ones. Consider this discourse use:

We have three strong arguments for you here today. I will show you why the Feminist Movement should not choices who actually engage in the playboy. And let me give three strong arguments about objectification. I will handle the first argument and my second speaker will handle the next argument. Now, before I move on to our three arguments, let me give a re – battle to some issues that the side Opposition brought. I am going to counteract this argument.

Such disjointed pieces of discourse may be the result of stress induced utterance emerging from a competitive argument in which the speaker is faced with a challenging disposition.

In this debate on academic genre where people are engaged in competitive language use, two types of repair could be identified: self – repair in which the current speaker who holds the floor realizes his/her errors or wishes to change the speech pattern to suit his/her intention, and other – initiated repair which is carried out by another speaker in another turn. In students' debates like the ones under investigation, this task is performed at various linguistic levels, ranging from word, clausal and even sentential. Sometimes, the entire contents may be

Figure 1. Disfluencies.

repaired by the fourth speaker as an extension to what precedes. However, the speaker who fulfills this obligation dare not make it explicit; otherwise the opponents might magnify it to be a weakness.

Unlike in conversations, the placement of a turn self – initiation correction within a turn is done immediately as seen in the examples above. However, self – corrections are still possible across turns and they are organized by reference to the previous speaker's points of arguments. The 'corrections' are positioned successfully (i.e. they occupy adjacency turns), and they are ordered, alternatively turn - by – turn positions. In other words, the different positions of the debaters invite the treatment involving a serial of ordering to repair where necessary. Unfortunately, first speakers of either side; proposition and opposition could not perform the function of correction because their duties precede every other speaker, and corrections entail 'something that went wrong'. But, the concept, self –correction' may have an extended meaning (in this study) to include a sort of 'polishing' what 'went' before as against a complete change, or restructure the discourse contents. This is conventionally is the basic role of the second speaker Opposition whose roles is elaborate on the earlier arguments put forward by the Member of Opposition. Consider these illustrations:

Our first Opposition told us about the right choice and so on. We will like to extend this, which the Government does - it is not their mandate and it is not in their role to detect subject of discussion.

The use of 'our first speakers told us'...is an acknowledgment of the contribution of the previous speakers, and the need to 'polish' it. In this regard, the original utterance (OU) does not necessarily contain trouble spot, or reparandum. Rather, the other speakers reinstate the (OU) in a new version in order to remind, add, etc. The reparandum may be anything ranging from

just a word to a whole stretch of discourse. The reason for the speaker's refusal to make outright correction is a deliberate debate strategy meant to hide one's own weakness which would be detrimental to the group scoring point.

In order for a particular speaker to make a 'self – correction' either partially or fully, the current speaker must firstly notice some troubles in the (OU) and be ready to interrupt herself/himself. This therefore calls for individual student debaters to imbibe the habit of self-monitoring their own speech as its failure has a great consequence on the team's scoring points.

Items on Figure 1 above indicate that the students' speeches are characterized by short unlexicalized disfluency with 67.8%, while short unlexicalized disfluency constitutes only 15%; repeats and self-correction have small marginal differences of 10.4 and 6.8 respectively.

A close study of disfluency reveals that there is no semantic difference between both long and short unlexicalized disfluencies in any speech environment. Rather, an individual speaker makes a choice between the two which is a matter of style. However, the degree of rambling for a particular lexical item determines the length and type of disfluency.

While speakers edit their productions, various techniques may be employed such as addition, elaboration, paraphrasing, reordering, replacement, restructuring, and substitution as indicated below.

While the above table provides solid understanding of the concept of repair, sometime, especially in a competitive communication exercise, it is worth noting that people for various reasons tend to be disorienting in their speeches as a result of unforeseen circumstances thereby resorting into repetition so as to create a sense of speech continuity which may enable the speaker to put up the subsequent utterance. In this regard, repetition

should not be considered as a repair device. Rather, it should be seen as one of the editing techniques that a speaker can employ while trying to arrange discourse properties. A similar observation can be made of paraphrase. To construct a paraphrasing statement entails making a discourse content so as to provide a better comprehension which may include adding or outright change in the form of semantics and grammar. Unlike other repairing devices mentioned above, after a paraphrase is carried out, original utterance remains unchanged because the speaker only carries out a selective sentence structures. As for other repair devices, the current researcher holds no further objections.

There are various conditions under which these maxims may be violated, or infringed upon. One of these is instrumental to the explanation of how implicatures are being communicated. For instance, when a speaker blatantly and openly says something which appears to be irrelevant, it can be assumed that if the speaker continues to observe the (CP) she/he really intends to communicate something which is relevant but does so implicitly.

Certain utterances which deviate from Gricean maxims and the repair mechanisms are presented in the following sub categorization. Incorrect discourse productions are speech quality deviation because the speaker's intended message does not correspond to syntactic representation. In communicative discourses produced under strict observations with high level of attentiveness ready to unveil a speaker's weaknesses, anxiety may feature thereby hampering the proper order of the discourse properties. This disorienting use of language may manifest through various means such as slips of the tongue, since people's linguistic performance does not always reflect their linguistic competence, Bergman et al (2007). In order to present a grammatically comprehensible message, a competitive language user needs to initiate a repair when he/she perceives wrong or disfluent speech which is capable of impeding the listener's understanding of the message. When a correction is carried, the appropriateness of the original utterance is repaired. See the following excerpts.

Excerpt (1). We say that there should be no sex- er sexual objectification because apparently, sexual objectification of women in any sphere takes away the individuality.

Excerpt (2). We can say that the feminist movement selects, selective arbitrary power basis.

Excerpt (3). I ask you whether she is ok with the woman going to the parliament in a short skirt, then the problem is women are taking, women – women's group really endorse.

In (1), there is a morphological misconstruction; since the speaker wanted to use the adjectival form of the 'sex' which is 'sexual' but misconstrued for its nominal variant which is a violation of a maxim of quality. However, other segments in the reparandum remain intact after the repair is carried out.

In (2 & 3), morphemic repairs have occurred. Specifically in (2), the intended word was *selective* an adjective, but what appears first is 'select', which is verb form. Again in (3), there is a violation of maxim of quality emerging from application of syntax. 'Whether' is used in reporting questions and it is used to express a doubt. Also, 'whether' is the most appropriately used word to introduce two or more possibilities. In this regard, dual observations could be made. First, the speaker is seeking for an answer which would have formed an interrogative sentence, but that possibility has been denied because of the absence of syntactic marker of question. Second, the speaker does not provide alternative options within which the respondent should select, and respond. While the speakers of utterances (1 and 2) make repairs because they 'self – monitored' their productions, in (3), the maxim of quality remains violated due to the speaker's inability to initiate a repair. Such a discourse use may be linked to the speaker's inefficient linguistic knowledge of English. For this reason, it is clear that the reparandum and the supposed alteration in the repair have given a different semantic interpretation. Therefore, repairing the utterance in (3) requires a complete restructuring of the syntax. Thus, it may be stated that the utterance which violates the maxim of quality includes language constructions in which interpretations do not correspond to the speaker's communicative intent. This is because every language especially English is endowed with structural conventions which make it possible for the speaker to select within the possible combinations that meet both linguistic and social requirements. However, it is sometimes difficult to ascertain the speaker's intent until a repair is established. Nonetheless, proper understanding of a language collocation, knowledge of syntax and semantics are germane in predicting speakers' intending lexical slots.

Speech with Maxim of Quantity Violations

Speakers do not only engage in repairs of their faulty constructions, but also initiate repair if they so feel that their speech is incomprehensible, i.e. the piece of information communicated is not adequate enough to fulfill intended desires. Repairs emerging from deficient information presentation tend to hamper listener's comprehension.

Maxim of quantity violation can be determined with recourse to the speaker's repair. In view of the complex nature of language components such as syntax, semantics, phonology, etc., it is very difficult to evaluate the adequacy of one's communication. However, the speaker's diction, listener's interest in the subject matter, background knowledge of the topic, and context of utterance may be among the factors that contribute to the identification of the speaker's intended quantity of speech.

Speaker's self – repair contributes immensely in determining his/her discourse adequacy. Consider the following excerpts in which various speakers use repair mechanisms in order to demonstrate their communicative intents. First, the repair mechanism of addition has been used to display intelligibility of the speech with which the speaker has inserted an extra constituents into the original utterance.

Excerpt (1) .We need an extremist – extremist idea – ideology.

Excerpt (2). Moving on to my third argument in terms of what is the benefit to the feminist movement per se and I spoke to you about before now. We believe that feminism has many negative perceptions.

In (1) the speaker uses 'extremist' which could mean either a noun or an adjective depends on what follows, but when the speaker adds another word 'idea'; it is apparent that s/he is referring to extremist which is an adjective. Yet, the utterance is not complete until the speaker adds the modifying element 'ideology' which narrows down the interpretation of the utterance to specific intention of the speaker. In (2), there is a complete digression from what the speaker says s/he is going to do. The speaker is expected to first dwell on the benefit of feminism, because s/he has made that promise earlier, 'moving on to my third argument...the benefit of feminism...' but that has been denied; s/he goes ahead to introduce a new thing which the listener is not expecting, ... 'feminism has many negative perceptions...' the listener wanders why the digression. This fragmented speech production can result in insufficient comprehension of information.

Speech with Maxim of Manner Violation

Speech is not only expected to follow the language conventions – adequate and informative, but logical, coherent and unified. If the information is properly coordinated, the utterance may have to be repaired by the speaker through the device of ordering where the speaker needs to make some structural adjustments. Like in other maxims explained above, speech manner deviation is sometime difficult to detect unless the speaker engages in self – repair as indicated below.

Excerpt (1). And also, what side proposition had told you today, side proposition is basically talking about this e:m – will – we will not allow this anti – religious videos because they incite people.

Excerpt (2). We say that because – because we begin at objectification. We say people – women objectifying themselves for in order to please men, ladies and gentlemen.

In both (1 and 2) above, the speakers suspend the earlier utterances because they find it necessary to make the information clearer, hence the adjustments in the sequences of the information for better representation

which accounts for the speakers' linguistic ability to convey the same messages in different ways. With this ability or rules, people can decide which linguistic property best suits their intentions to match the syntax, phonology, morphology and semantics of the language. However, people's linguistic performance sometime does not reflect their understanding as speeches may be hampered by disorienting situations as demonstrated above. Fortunately, people often self – monitor their utterances, and unexpected utterances if they occur are repaired.

CONCLUSION

Debate genres are easy to recognize intuitively but difficult to define due to typical characteristics which are not only unique to them; it is their relative prominence, combination, and functions.

From pragma-linguistic perspective, world university students' debate discourse belonged to the genre of politics because it displayed particular institutionalized discursive features and ritualized interaction strategies, while complying with and/or circumventing a number of specific rules and constraints. Furthermore, the discursive interaction of the debate genre was marked by its social role-based commitment, by dialogically shaped institutional confrontation between the proposition and the opposition team members, and through the awareness of acting in front of both co-debaters and other non- debating people. The internal structure consisted of overall elements such as words production by the participants, specific regulations of dialogicity, argument strategies, persuasive techniques, and repair approaches. Also contained in this level were verbal pauses or hesitations.

The students' debate competitive speeches were usually characterized by disfluency of varied types which may be caused by a lot of factors such as uncertainty, unfamiliar discourse type, disruption, poor vocabularies, etc. Disfluency facilitates comprehension and allows listeners to amend their predictions about what might be uttered next. In spite hampering communication, disfluency assists listeners to evaluate confidence of the speakers.

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